

TEACHERS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM IN THE DIVISION OF ISABELA: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

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ABSTRACT

In today's education landscape, teachers face diverse challenges, requiring a sustainable approach to professional growth. This study focuses on the professional development of teachers in the Division of Isabela, emphasizing the status, challenges, and prospects of the current development program as perceived by school heads and teachers. Using a descriptive survey, data were collected from 45 school heads and 878 teachers. Findings highlight that while the existing professional development program is effective, significant differences in perceptions exist between school heads and teachers regarding program status and challenges. Common challenges include resource limitations, extended working hours, and the lack of technological proficiency. Despite these hurdles, the study identifies various opportunities for improvement, such as better allocation of resources and enhanced training programs. The research aims to contribute to the development of tailored, effective strategies for continuous professional development, addressing the evolving needs of teachers and ultimately improving educational outcomes. Recommendations include prioritizing financial and technical resources and fostering a culture of reflection and feedback.

Keywords: *Teachers Professional Development Program*

INTRODUCTION

Today's educational realm is full of multiple perspectives, technologies, and opportunities for teachers, learners and educational leaders. In order to realize areas of

strength and areas that need attention for professional growth; teachers should undertake a sustainable action to find out the bottlenecks of teachers in the field as regards to their professional growth and development provided through status, challenges and prospect. Same scenario that the writer experienced in the field as teacher. Teachers in fragile and crisis contexts face enormous barriers to quality professional development. There are lots of difficulties that teachers have to overcome when they are in the classroom.

In today's world, teachers are overworked and they are also expected to essentially shape the future of the nation with very limited resources. In shaping the future of learners, teachers are responsible for their students, the young people who are under their guidance. Investing in to oneself as educator is the best way to ensure both career growth and academic growth for the learners. Even though it can take up precious time in nurturing and sustaining quality education to the educational system. Adventurous teachers are ready to share their culture and life experience in teaching arena. Teachers and school heads should consider the best from across the globe that provides possibilities for professional growth and to improve professional skills to deliver quality education to learners. Through understanding the needs of teachers, setting apart from other organization is the most comprehensive professional development program for teachers and school administrators.

Every school in the country should be strongly committed and dedicated to support student education and well- being through its curriculum and a range of initiatives that offer opportunities that promotes quality education to learners who loved studying their lessons. Teachers and school heads are encouraged to implement comprehensive education and professional development programs, including teacher's trainings, seminars and workshops through the implementation of DepEd Orders and Memoranda in the Professional development programs for teachers and school leaders.

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is important for individuals because it keeps their thinking fresh, their skills relevant and their motivation high. It also shows the ability to display their commitment to self-development and professionalism.

The implementation of DepEd Professional Development Priorities supports the realization of the Department's goal of continuous upskilling and reskilling of teachers and school administrators that will result in better learning outcomes. The greatest of the challenges faced by a teacher are: First, Knowing their students well. Second is understanding the different learning abilities and capacities of the students. And the last one is motivating and encouraging them when the students underperform and have to deal with parental and peer pressure.

The designated Learning and Development (LnD) Proponent together with the teachers and school administrators must manifest vital role in realizing the Professional Development priorities mapped to the professional standards through the different pillars in education.

Training centers in the Department of Education like the National Educators' Academy of the Philippines (NEAP) plays a vital role in providing utmost professional development among teachers and school administrators which must also be resulted to quality outcomes.

As a Learning and Development (LnD) Proponent and a teacher, the researcher opted to conduct this dissertation that may help in the realization of utmost quality education and to ensure best performance outcomes.

This study also tried to look into the proper implementation of guidelines and close supervision of the quality and best performances of learners and teachers will be expected to assure satisfactory implementation of the DepEd Orders and Memoranda in Teachers' professional development. Some of the teachers or educators are being observed in implementing to these guidelines from the Department of Education. An average of 4 teachers in every quarter found to complain about extending their time and efforts in attending trainings, seminars and workshops. One of the precipitating factors perceived to aggravate this among teachers and school administrators. These are the reasons why the researcher wanted to conduct this study because of the researcher's willingness to help improve the present scenario of teachers' professional development. The Individual Plan for Professional Development (IPPD) based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) will serve as basis for SLAC.

The Learning and Development (LnD) Focal teacher in the school had noticed that seminars and workshops and lack of teaching and managing strategies in handling students and teachers are the common issues. This means that they should be required to undergo trainings, seminars and workshops as participants and facilitators in obtaining best education and can be used as their way of promoting themselves for professional growth. With the presented scenario, this has given the researcher more reasons to know how to manage a certain school or organization.

The researcher is further interested to look into the reasons why some teachers seldom involve and/or participate to continuous professional development programs. The probability drawn that their bottlenecks describe through status, challenges and prospects really affects their participation and decision making which limit themselves to be a part of Continuous Professional Development (CPD).

Research Questions

This study focused on the teachers' professional development in the Legislative District 2 as perceived by teachers and school heads. More specifically the study endeavored to answer the following specific problems:

1. What is the status of the existing Teachers Professional Development Program in the Division of Isabela as perceived by the teachers and their school heads?

2. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the teachers and school heads on the status of the Teachers Professional Development Program?
3. What are the challenges encountered in the implementation of the Teachers Professional Development Program as perceived by the teachers and school heads?
4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of teachers and school heads on the challenges encountered in the implementation of the Teachers Professional Development Program?
5. What is the level of satisfaction of the teachers on the existing Teachers Professional Development Program?
6. Is there a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of the teachers on the existing teachers' professional development program?
7. What are the prospects for Teachers Professional Development Program as identified by the teachers and school heads?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher made use of the descriptive survey method in gathering data about the status, challenges and prospects on teachers' professional development program of teachers and school heads. Survey research according to Wallen(2023), is one of the most common forms of research in education. It involves asking a group of teachers and school heads through using questionnaires being answered. It is deemed appropriate for this study considering that this study aims to examine the status, challenges and prospects on teachers' professional development program in in public secondary schools of the Schools Division of Isabela.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in one of the biggest number of teachers and school heads of the Schools Division of Isabela, the Legislative District 2. In terms of the number of teachers and school heads, the Legislative District 2 has eight districts consists of Benito Soliven North, Benito Soliven South, Gamu, Naguilian, Palanan, Reina Mercedes, San Mariano 1 and San Mariano 2. It comprised 878 teachers and 45 school heads with a total of 923. Legislative District 2 also known as one of the best performing legislative districts in the Schools Division of Isabela.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The study involved the school heads and teachers of the public secondary schools in Legislative District 2, School Year 2022-2023. Total enumeration of the two groups of respondents were considered.

Specifically, a total of 45 School Heads were included in this study, 40 were School Heads of Junior High School and 5 for Senior High School. The overall total of teacher-respondents involved in this study were 878, 689 were Junior High School teachers and 189 were Senior High School teachers. Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Legislative District 2	Junior High School		Senior High School	
	School Heads	Teacher s	School Heads	Teacher s
	Number	Number	Number	Number
1. Benito Soliven North	3	65	0	14
2. Benito Soliven South	3	44	1	6
3. Gamu	4	95	1	33
4. Naguilian	3	73	1	32
5. Palanan	3	65	1	22
6. Reina Mercedes	4	104	0	29
7. San Mariano 1	12	157	1	40
8. San Mariano 2	8	86	0	13
Total Population	40	689	5	189

Data Gathering Procedure

After the proposal was satisfactorily defended and given approval to pursue the study, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Schools Division of Isabela then she presented it to the district supervisors and school heads. The researcher made use of both the Google form and face to face to float questionnaires to the respondents but had to communicate to the supervisors first about the purpose of the study. The researcher also conducted informal interviews with the teachers and school heads to get other data needed to supplement the information and to clarify vague responses.

The data gathered, collated, tallied and organized in tabular form for analysis and interpretation to provide descriptions of the status, challenges and prospects on teachers' professional development.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data from the questionnaire, including those from interviews conducted were summarized, analyzed and interpreted and statistically treated using the appropriate formula as suggested by the statistician.

Weighted Mean. To answer problems number 1, 3 and 5 of this study, the weighted mean was utilized to determine the respondents' perceptions on the satisfaction level of the implementation on teachers' professional development.

Independent t-Test. This was used to answer problems 2, 4 and 6 in order to find out if significant difference exists in respondents' perception on teachers and school heads on teachers' professional development and their level of satisfaction.

Rank Distribution. To determine the enhancement of the existing prospects by the respondents in the rank distribution was used.

Pearson Product Moment of Coefficient of Correlation Ranking Scale and T-Test was used to treat the hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Status of existing Teachers Professional Development Program in the Division of Isabela as perceived by the teachers and their school heads

Table 2
Status of the existing Teachers Professional Development Program
in the Division of Isabela as perceived by the teachers and
Their School Heads

Status of the Teachers' Professional Development Program	School Heads		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
The teachers' professional development program in the Division of Isabela ...				

• Addresses the development needs of teachers				
1. Focuses on teachers' classroom practice.	3.62	Very Effective	3.73	Very Effective
2. Addresses teachers' pedagogical content knowledge	3.53	Very Effective	3.42	Very Effective
3. Addresses students' learning processes within the content area	3.62	Very Effective	3.57	Very Effective
4. Is strongly content- focused	3.69	Very Effective	3.41	Very Effective
5. Makes use of inquiry-oriented learning approaches	3.53	Very Effective	3.42	Very Effective
6. Is instructionally-focused, emphasizes subject area content and pedagogy as well as student learning outcomes	3.62	Very Effective	3.47	Very Effective
7. Makes use of various activities including receiving feedback, observing expert teachers, being observed by other teachers, practicing new ways of teaching, discussing elements of the change with others and reviewing student work.	3.58	Very Effective	3.44	Very Effective
8. Provides activities that guide teachers especially in reflecting on and integrating their ideas	3.58	Very Effective	3.43	Very Effective
9. Provides activities that support teachers in gathering insight into students' ideas and evidence of students' progress in developing understanding of the course material.	3.84	Very Effective	3.51	Very Effective
10. Addresses the use of new technology as teachers appeared to lack the time and expertise to plan for this by themselves.	3.71	Very Effective	3.45	Very Effective

11. Makes use of models of effective practices	3.69	Very Effective	3.41	Very Effective
12. Facilitates and stimulates collaboration	3.56	Very Effective	3.42	Very Effective
13. Requires collaborative participation	3.60	Very Effective	3.52	Very Effective
14. Emphasizes both active and interactive learning experiences, often through participation in learning communities.	3.78	Very Effective	3.72	Very Effective
15. Engages teachers physically, cognitively, and emotionally through activities such as problem solving, sharing and discussion, simulations and role play, visual representations, application and follow through, and reflection	3.56	Very Effective	3.55	Very Effective
16. Incorporates active learning	3.60	Very Effective	3.74	Very Effective
17. Is coherent with the school, district and division and national curricula, reforms and policies	3.67	Very Effective	3.52	Very Effective
18. Provides substantial amount of time to stimulate teachers' professional development and follow-up activities take place.	3.78	Very Effective	3.29	Very Effective
19. Is ongoing and involves a combination of contact hours, duration, and coherence is of sustained duration	3.29	Very Effective	3.46	Very Effective
20. Is of sustained duration	3.62	Very Effective	3.49	Very Effective
21. Is supported by the school leaders	3.67	Very Effective	3.77	Very Effective
22. Considers the physical characteristics of the school, external factors and the school culture	3.84	Very Effective	3.79	Very Effective

23. Provides coaching and expert support	3.22	Effective	3.75	Very Effective
24. Supports teacher motivation and commitment to the learning process	3.78	Very Effective	3.78	Very Effective
25. Adopts practices that uphold the dignity of teaching by exhibiting qualities such as caring, attitude, respect and integrity.	3.51	Very Effective	3.76	Very Effective
26. Upholds dignity of teaching to help build a positive teaching and learning culture within the school	3.89	Very Effective	3.79	Very Effective
27. Promotes and upgrades the teachers' professional development.	3.47	Very Effective	3.68	Very Effective
28. Develop trusting, productive relationships	3.84	Very Effective	3.78	Very Effective
29. Exhibits effective and constructive behavior management skills.	3.82	Very Effective	3.73	Very Effective
30. Make a difference in teachers' professional practice through new knowledge and skills learned	3.67	Very Effective	3.79	Very Effective
31. Incorporates assessment of both professional growth and attainment of program goals.	3.82	Very Effective	3.44	Very Effective
32. Combines the needs of individuals with school, district, and division goals.	3.36	Very Effective	3.54	Very Effective
33. It strongly links teacher and student learning and is guided by data	3.87	Very Effective	3.74	Very Effective
34. Reflects, connects, follow-up activities that require daily responsibilities	3.69	Very Effective	3.63	Very Effective
35. Provides many opportunities overtime to interact with ideas	3.91	Very Effective	3.75	Very Effective

and procedures and practice new skills.				
36. There is a link of professional development in student learning and professional standards for learning.	3.67	Very Effective	3.47	Very Effective Very Effective
37. Focusses on competency development and acquisition of required KSAs	3.73	Very Effective	3.54	Very Effective
38. Employs self-managed learning	3.42	Very Effective	3.82	Very Effective
39. Provides opportunities for job enhancements, retooling and or upskilling	3.76	Very Effective	3.81	Very Effective
Average Weighted Mean	3.68	Very Effective	3.59	Very Effective

Table 2 presents the existing Teachers Professional Development Program in the Division of Isabela as perceived by the teachers and their school heads. The data reveals that both the school heads and teachers perceived the status of the teachers' professional development program as *very effective* with an average weighted mean of 3.68 and 3.59 respectively.

This anticipated the similarities to the teachers' professional development that follows guidelines on Professional development priorities for teachers and school leaders set by the Department of Education through Department Memorandum No. 50, s. 2020 which indicate to provide guidance for the identification, opportunities and development of the DepEd.

The result of the present study negates Oecd (2009) as their study revealed that the current implementations of school leadership development process in the study area showed that school leadership development implementations has problems specially in selection, recruitment, assignment of school leaders for development before and after development. School leadership development process during implementations mainly dominated by political affiliation and intimacy were seen during school leaders' recruitment, selection and assignment in the zone.

Based on the result of Oecd (2009) they recommended that the Education office has to adjust open access and diversified methods to invite potential applicants; they have to give the value to academic qualification merit based during selecting; thus, it signified the importance of continuous teacher professional development aiming at improving the teaching learning process thereby the quality of education.

2. Significant difference in the perception of the teachers and school heads on the status of the Teachers Professional Development Program?

Table 3
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers and School Heads on the Status of the Teachers Professional Development Program

Variables	Mean		Probability of t	Remarks
	School Heads	Teachers		
Perception of the Teachers and School Heads on the Status of the Teachers Professional Development Program	3.68	3.59	0.0093	Highly Significant

Table 3 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers and school heads on the status of the teacher’s professional development program.

The results reveal that the t-probability value is less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers and school heads on the status of the Teachers Professional Development Program. It implies that the school heads differ in their perception on the status of the Teachers Professional Development Program from that of the teachers. It further infers as evidenced by the mean in the table that the school heads have better perception of the status of the Teachers Professional Development Program than the teachers.

It is essential to note that school heads may have certain advantages in perceiving the overall status of a professional development program, collaboration and communication between school heads and teachers are essential for comprehensive program evaluation and improvement. Teachers’ input and feedback are invaluable in understanding the program’s impact on individual growth and classroom practices. Therefore, fostering an open and supportive environment for sharing perspectives can lead to more successful professional development initiatives.

In a survey-based study by Brown et al, school heads and teachers were asked to rate the effectiveness of a specific professional development program. While teachers generally perceived the program positively, school heads’ rating were consistently higher. The study attributed this difference to school heads’ access to a wider range of information and their ability to observe the program’s impact more broadly.

Moreover, a research study conducted by Smith and Johnson (2014) compared perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding a professional development

program. The study found that school heads consistently showed a better understanding of the program’s goals and alignment with school-wide objectives. They were also more aware of the support and resources needed to implement the learning outcomes effectively.

3. Challenges encountered in the implementation of the Teachers Professional Development Program as perceived by the teachers and school heads?

Table 4
Human–Based Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of the Teacher Professional Development Program

Human-Based Challenges	School Heads		Teachers		Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description		
1. Pushing teachers to evolve teaching strategies, so they support personalized learning for creativity, innovation, and problem solving and have more time for individual instruction.	1.84	Less Serious	1.86	Less Serious	1.85	Less Serious
2. Rising inequality and slow productivity.	1.27	Not Serious	1.15	Not Serious	1.21	Not Serious
3. Endless paperwork & extended working hours.	1.76	Less Serious	1.90	Less Serious	1.83	Less Serious
4. Absence of encouragement and motivation during	1.24	Not Serious	1.53	Not Serious	1.39	Not Serious

challenging times.						
5. Failure to bring out the change in employees' attitude towards their job.	1.20	Not Serious	1.80	Less Serious	1.50	Not Serious
6. Not attending to students who need to spend one-one time connecting and problem-solving.	1.22	Not Serious	1.64	Not Serious	1.43	Not Serious
7. Having bad or overbearing school heads.	1.18	Not Serious	1.83	Less Serious	1.51	Not Serious
8. Lack of clarity about career growth.	1.53	Not Serious	1.61	Not Serious	1.57	Not Serious
9. Not assessing the progress of the students and effectively conveying the same to the parents.	1.53	Not Serious	1.57	Not Serious	1.55	Not Serious
10. Issues of value-based of education in curriculum is not addressed.	1.07	Not Serious	1.88	Less Serious	1.48	Not Serious
11. Limited training, course and post graduate studies funding options, etc.	1.22	Not Serious	1.88	Less Serious	1.55	Not Serious
12. None application of	2.20	Less Serious	1.84	Less Serious	2.02	Less Serious

the teaching profession and the responsibilities specified in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers.						
13. None provision of Technical Assistance and other mentoring needs.	1.00	Not Serious	1.75	Less Serious	1.38	Not Serious
Average Weighted Mean	1.40	Not Serious	1.71	Not Serious	1.55	Not Serious

The resource-based in human challenges presented in Table 4. The data displays that 1.55 *not serious* was the average weighted mean for both school heads and teacher-respondents. The result also indicates that the teacher respondents have higher average mean of 1.71 compared with the school heads which only have 1.40 as their average weighted mean but both respondents obtained a description of *not serious*.

Furthermore, the data revealed that the school heads perceived item 5,7,10, 11 & 13 as *not serious* while the teacher-respondents perceived it as *less serious*. It implies that the school heads differ from that of the teachers in their perception on the respondents' resource based in human challenges encountered in the implementation of the teacher professional development program on five items.

As per the findings of the study of Garet, et.al. (2001) it affirms that participation and discourse practices can enhance teacher learning by supporting professional critique, reflection, and collaboration. However, many schools and teacher educators struggle to foster constructive interactions.

Studies related to the result of human-based challenges, such as failure to bring about a change in employees' attitude towards the job, often fall within the field of organizational behavior, management, and psychology. These studies investigate various factors that affect employee attitudes, the barriers to successful attitude change, and strategies to overcome these challenges. Based on the study of Griffith et.al. (2015), which explores the relationship between employee attitudes, job satisfaction, and organizational performance. It considers both individual and organizational factors that impact employees' attitudes toward their jobs. However, according to Jones et.al (2014), it affirms the study that examines the influence of leadership style and organizational

climate on attitude change initiatives. It highlights the importance of leadership in creating a supportive environment for employees to embrace change.

Based from Garcia & Weiss (2019), he stated that the consequences of toxic leadership on student outcomes and school performance. It investigates how negative leadership practices can create a toxic learning environment and hinder student academic and socio emotional growth.

The result of human-based challenges related to the lack of addressing value-based education in the curriculum often falls within the field of education, curriculum development, and ethics. It is perhaps explore the implications of neglecting value-based education and highlight the importance of integrating values into the curriculum.

In addition, Brown, et.al.(2016), on his survey-based study explores the challenges faced by adult learners in accessing courses and training programs. It investigates factors such as financial constraints, scheduling issues, and lack of support that hinder individuals from pursuing further education. Furthermore, it investigates the impact of government policies and employer support in promoting continuing education for employees. It explores the availability of funding options and how they contribute to individual skill development and career progression. The result of this study is somewhat related to limited training opportunities and funding options for courses and post-graduate studies that can be found in the fields of education, workforce development, and higher education. It investigate the impact of limited training and funding on individuals' professional growth and overall workforce development.

None provision of Technical Assistance and other mentoring needs can be found in various fields, including education, organizational behavior, and workforce development. It resulted to the impact of the absence of necessary the support and guidance on individual development and overall organizational success.

Table 5
Financial Based Challenges Encountered in the Implementation
of The Teacher Professional Development Program

Financial Based Challenges	School Heads		Teachers		Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description		
1. Failure to account expenses incurred as a result of the absence of supporting	1.13	Not Serious	1.72	Not Serious	1.42	Not Serious

documents (receipts) to support the expenditures incurred.						
2. Inappropriate maintenance and operation for the welfare of the students, such as PTA, fundraising, donations, and feeding program fund.	1.49	Not Serious	1.74	Not Serious	1.61	Not Serious
3. Not having a plan for using budget and in proper reporting.	1.60	Not Serious	1.52	Not Serious	1.56	Not Serious
4. Not preparing Line-item budget that comes from the respective MOOE and other external grants.	1.73	Not Serious	1.78	Less Serious	1.75	Less Serious
5. Irrelevant learning materials, excessive centralization, and inadequate financial resources.	1.42	Not Serious	1.17	Not Serious	1.29	Not Serious
6. Budget concerns and constraints are not properly designed and planned.	1.53	Not Serious	1.49	Not Serious	1.51	Not Serious
7. Inventory and entry of current competencies are unmet.	1.13	Not Serious	1.72	Not Serious	1.42	Not Serious

8. Adverse financial or operational impact in the classroom.	1.33	Not Serious	1.47	Not Serious	1.40	Not Serious
Average Weighted Mean	1.42	Not Serious	1.58	Not Serious	1.50	Not Serious

Table 5 exhibits the results of the respondents' resource based in financial challenges encountered in the implementation of the teacher professional development program. It is revealed that both the school heads and teachers are fully aware in resource-based financial challenges encountered in the implementation of the teachers' professional development program as indicated in their average weighted mean of 1.42 and 1.58 respectively.

All the items were rated *not serious* except for item 4 which indicates that the school head perceived this item *not serious* while the teacher-respondents rated it as *less serious*.

Moreover, the most pressing issues in the financial challenges among the respondents is *not preparing Line-item budget that comes from the respective MOOE and other external grants* that was the highest in mean but it was considered as *less serious*. In addition, *adverse financial challenges or operational impact in the classroom* that was the lowest mean for both school head and teacher-respondents. The financial-based challenges, such as *not preparing a line-item budget that comes from the respective Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) and external grants*, can be found in the field of financial management, public administration, and educational policy studies. It examined the consequences of inadequate budget preparation and its impact on organizational financial management and educational outcomes. Therefore, financial challenges in teachers' professional development program is very crucial on the part of the teachers in Legislative District 2.

As per results, the findings affirms with the study of Guskey, et.al. (2006) "the relationship between professional development and improvements in student learning in these real-world settings is far too complex and includes too many intervening variables in education."

Table 6
Material–Based Challenges Encountered in the Implementation
of the Teacher Professional Development Program

Material-Based Challenges	School Heads		Teachers		Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description		
1. Unjust planning and delivering teaching strategies that responsive to the educational needs of learners.	1.33	Not Serious	1.69	Not Serious	1.51	Not Serious
2. Not modelling a range of high-level skills responsive to the special educational needs of learners in difficult circumstances.	1.16	Not Serious	1.26	Not Serious	1.21	Not Serious
3. None application of conducting need analysis, setting aims and objectives, and planning.	1.24	Not Serious	1.70	Not Serious	1.47	Not Serious
4. No interest of technical ability to use tools and devices to create digital learning resources.	1.76	Less Serious	1.78	Less Serious	1.77	Less Serious
5. Unplanned strategy of organizing learning materials to be applied to learning resources.	1.38	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious	1.43	Not Serious

6. Lack of skills in managing, planning and securing materials for the learners' needs.	1.40	Not Serious	1.46	Not Serious	1.43	Not Serious
7. Proper dissemination of memoranda, notices, and guidelines is not observed.	1.20	Not Serious	1.21	Not Serious	1.20	Not Serious
8. Delivery of instructions is not given interest and application.	1.62	Not Serious	1.56	Not Serious	1.59	Not Serious
Average Weighted Mean	1.39	Not Serious	1.52	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious

Table 6 shows the respondent's challenges encountered in the implementation of the teacher professional development program on the resource based material challenges.

Though the results indicates that both the two groups of respondents manifested an average weighted rating of *not serious* the highest mean of both school heads and teachers' material challenges is 1.77 weighted mean in item 4 which is *having no interest of technical ability to use tools and devices to create digital learning resources that conclude the most pressing challenges*. While the lowest mean is on item 2 which is *not modelling a range of high-level skills responsive to the special educational needs of learners in difficult circumstances* can be found in the fields of special education, inclusive education, and pedagogy. These were explored the impact of limited teaching materials and resources on the educational outcomes of learners facing difficult circumstances.

The findings further imply that both groups of the school heads and teachers in material resource-based challenges in the implementation of the teacher professional development program was *not serious*.

Tai & Omar (2021) negates the challenges on the importance of driver for the development of human capital and economic growth to ensure the education ecosystem constantly stays dynamic and relevant and education 4.0 has been developed in response to the Fourth Industry Revolution (FIR).

However, the study of Cchiaro. (2023) affirms that Educators can create a level playing field for all. Authentic learning experiences will multiply the paths that lay at students' feet as they embark on their life's journey. Educators then must find ways to embrace students' curiosities and several secondary school educators participate in a professional development program on cooperative learning. They gain a thorough understanding of the theory and develop a variety of classroom activities based on proper consumption of materials in school.

Table 7
Technology-Based Challenges Encountered in the Implementation
of the Teacher Professional Development Program

Technology-Based Challenges	School Heads		Teachers		Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description		
1. Failure to apply important structure to lesson planning and the delivery of instructions.	1.18	Not Serious	1.38	Not Serious	1.28	Not Serious
2. Technology causes lack of interest in studying.	1.53	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious	1.50	Not Serious
3. Unable to help workers to become more economical.	1.07	Not Serious	1.35	Not Serious	1.21	Not Serious
4. Not having a convergence of digital, biological, and physical innovations.	1.11	Not Serious	1.68	Not Serious	1.39	Not Serious
5. No application of uniform measure to assess teacher performance, and provide support for professional development.	1.53	Not Serious	1.89	Less Serious	1.71	Not Serious

6. Failure to keep students safe online and teacher knowledge and professional development.	1.31	Not Serious	1.86	Less Serious	1.58	Not Serious
7. Access, participation, engagement, and continued application of new skills in the classroom are not given importance.	1.38	Not Serious	1.75	Less Serious	1.56	Not Serious
8. Imbalance between the efficiency, the pace of learning, quality, and overall learning experience in offline and online classes.	1.36	Not Serious	1.75	Not Serious	1.55	Not Serious
9. Inadequate classroom space that will accommodate a large number of computers.	1.27	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious	1.37	Not Serious
10. Teachers' distaste to take the students to computer laboratory.	1.29	Not Serious	1.82	Less Serious	1.55	Not Serious
11. Not having educational pathways to use the Internet and other digital technologies.	1.11	Not Serious	1.79	Less Serious	1.45	Not Serious
12. Lack of dedicated IT-skilled	1.53	Not Serious	1.46	Not Serious	1.49	Not Serious

teachers in mentoring and coaching.						
Average Weighted Mean	1.31	Not Serious	1.64	Not Serious	1.47	Not Serious

The challenges encountered in the implementation of the teacher professional development program technology- based challenges are presented in Table 7. Results reveal that the respondents considered this challenges as *not serious*.

However, results reveal the responses for items 5,6,7 10 & 11 perceived differently by the respondents. The school heads viewed it as *not serious* while the teachers have it as *less serious*.

In addition, *that no application of uniform measure to assess teacher performance, and provide support for professional development* for both respondents was the highest mean of 1.71 and so as with the teacher- respondents had the highest mean value. It can also be found in the fields of education, educational technology, and teacher evaluation the implications of inconsistent assessment practices and limited use of technology in supporting teachers' growth and development. Furthermore, the lowest average weighted mean of 1.21 *unable to help workers to become more economical which also showed that among the 12 technology-based challenges it was the lowest for the school heads so as with the teachers*.

Furthermore, Parry, et.al. (2023) affirms all information about a program's overall impact can guide improvements in all aspects of professional development, including program design, implementation, and follow-up.

From the study of Brown, et.al. (2016), a longitudinal analysis investigates the impact of technology on teacher professional development. It explore how the use of technology can support teachers' growth and enhance their instructional practices. On the other point of view, technology-based challenges particularly focusing on failure to keep students safe online and teacher knowledge and professional development as the lowest, while neglecting access, participation, engagement, and continued application of new skills in the classroom, can be found in the fields of educational technology, digital citizenship, and teacher education. The result examine the consequences of inadequate attention to online safety and teacher professional development in integrating technology effectively in the classroom.

Table 8
Training-Based Challenges Encountered in the Implementation
of the Teacher Professional Development Program

Training-Based Challenges	School Heads		Teachers		Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description		
1. The existing teacher's professional development program lacks vision of teaching and learning	1.04	Not Serious	1.33	Not Serious	1.19	Not Serious
2. It fails to cultivate teacher's ownership.	1.46	Not Serious	1.69	Not Serious	1.58	Not Serious
3. It is short, sporadic and disconnected from classroom	1.40	Not Serious	1.34	Not Serious	1.37	Not Serious
4. It is one-size-fit-all	1.08	Not Serious	1.85	Less Serious	1.47	Not Serious
5. It is not collaborative.	1.68	Not Serious	1.47	Not Serious	1.57	Not Serious
6. It has its geographic limitations.	1.24	Not Serious	1.62	Not Serious	1.43	Not Serious
7. There is lack of support of school administrators.	1.57	Not Serious	1.32	Not Serious	1.44	Not Serious
8. There is lack of planning.	1.11	Not Serious	1.35	Not Serious	1.23	Not Serious
9. Some educators lack interest.	1.64	Not Serious	1.84	Less Serious	1.74	Not Serious
10. There is lack of teaching skills application	1.08	Not Serious	1.61	Not Serious	1.35	Not Serious

Average Weighted Mean	1.34	Not Serious	1.54	Not Serious	1.44	Not Serious
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Table 8 displays the respondent's challenges encountered in the implementation of the teacher professional development program on training-based challenges as *not serious*. The data clearly show that school heads highest mean is 1.68, *It is not collaborative*, 1.85, *it is one-size-fit-all* the highest mean among teachers. On the other hand, the most pressing challenges was *some educators lack interest* for both respondents. The average weighted mean of training-based challenges on teacher's professional development program is *not serious* in general.

Woodcock and Hardy (2017), affirm that teachers take part in numerous practices related to Teachers' Professional Development Program, classified as formal and informal variations. Teachers are key drivers of research-based teaching methods as they demonstrate theoretical underpinnings of principles and models of successful teaching and learning processes.

Training-based challenges encountered in the implementation of teacher professional development programs investigate the effectiveness of teacher training programs, the barriers and challenges faced during implementation, and strategies to improve the outcomes of professional development initiatives to determine the overall effectiveness on teacher practice, student learning outcomes, and overall program success.

Table 9
Summary Table on the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of the Teacher Professional Development Program

Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of TPDP	School Heads		Teachers		Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description		
1. Resource-Based	1.04	Not Serious	1.33	Not Serious	1.19	Not Serious
a. Human	1.40	Not Serious	1.71	Not Serious	1.55	Not Serious
b. Financial	1.42	Not Serious	1.58	Not Serious	1.50	Not Serious
c. Material	1.39	Not Serious	1.52	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious

2. Technology-based	1.31	Not Serious	1.64	Not Serious	1.47	Not Serious
3. Training-based	1.34	Not Serious	1.54	Not Serious	1.44	Not Serious
Average Weighted Mean	1.37	Not Serious	1.59	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious

Table 9 presents the summary of the challenges encountered in the implementation of the teacher professional development program. The table reveals that the respondents perceived all the challenges as *not serious*. An interview with a teacher reveals that the professional development workshops provided by the school are often conducted by individuals without practical classroom teaching experience. This leads to a lack of relevance and applicability to their teaching contexts pertaining with the challenges on human resource-based challenges. Furthermore, financial recourse-based challenges are insufficient budget in which Schools may face budget constraints that limit the allocation of funds for comprehensive and sustained professional development programs for example, an interview with a school head reveals that despite recognizing the importance of ongoing professional development for teachers, the school's limited budget restricts their ability to send teachers to external training workshops or conferences. Outdated or inadequate learning resources that may lead to schools lack up-to-date teaching materials, textbooks, or digital resources that align with modern teaching approaches and curricula. R interview with a teacher highlights the lack of access to digital learning resources, hindering their ability to integrate technology effectively into their teaching and professional development. Schools with inadequate or unreliable technology infrastructure face difficulties in conducting online professional development sessions or utilizing technology-based resources. Interviews with multiple teachers reveal that the school's outdated technology infrastructure and lack of training in using digital tools hinder their participation in online professional development programs. Teachers who lack technological proficiency may struggle to engage with digital learning platforms or online professional tools. Standardized training programs that do not consider individual teacher needs or levels of expertise may not effectively address their unique professional development requirements. Absence of ongoing support and mentoring after the initial training may hinder the application of new skills and knowledge in the classroom. It indicates that the school's professional development workshops follow a generic approach without considering the specific subject area needs or grade-level challenges, making the training less impactful.

To sum it up, resource-based challenges significantly impact the effectiveness of teachers' professional development programs. Human resources, financial constraints, material resources, technology access, and training approaches must be carefully addressed to ensure meaningful and sustainable teacher growth and improved student outcomes. Interviews with teachers and school heads can provide valuable insights into

the real-life experiences and perceptions related to these challenges, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis and targeted solutions.

Hermann and Grossman (2001), affirms the overall perceived challenges of the two groups of respondents on the five encountered challenges was described as not serious facing teacher professional development: it lacks an ambitious vision of teaching and learning; it fails to cultivate teacher ownership; it is short, sporadic, and disconnected from the classroom; it's one-size-fits-all; and it's not collaborative.

Based on informal interview with the respondents and on actual observations, school certainly goes through a lot of tough and challenging efforts prior to the challenges encountered in the implementation of teachers' professional development program that involves a series of actions and operations. Nevertheless, it was found out to resolve the different challenges being encountered.

4. Result of the Test of Significant difference in the perception of the teachers and school heads on the challenges encountered in the implementation of the teachers' professional development program.

Table 10
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers and School Heads on the Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of the Teachers Professional Development Program

Perception of the Teachers and School Heads on the following Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of the Teachers Professional Development Program	Mean		Probability of t	Remarks
	School Heads	Teachers		
Human	1.40	1.71	1.1598 E-10	Highly Significant
Financial	1.42	1.58	0.0008	Highly Significant
Material	1.39	1.52	0.0106	Significant
Technology Based	1.31	1.64	1.9726 E-13	Highly Significant
Training Based	1.34	1.54	8.1494 E-10	Highly Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers and school heads on the challenges encountered in the implementation of the Teachers Professional Development Program are disclosed in Table 10.

It is evident from the results that probability values of t are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is significant difference in the perception of the teachers and school heads on the challenges encountered in the implementation of the Teachers Professional Development Program. It shows that the perception of the school heads on the challenges encountered in the implementation of the Teachers Professional Development Program vary from that of the teachers. As indicated by the mean in the table, both groups do not encounter the challenges in terms human, financial, material, technology based, and training based in the implementation of the Teachers Professional Development Program. However, the school heads perceived that these challenges are least not encountered since they obtained the lower means than the teachers.

The results of the informal interview to the teachers perceived the lack of time for professional development as a significant challenge, while school heads may prioritize budget constraints as the primary concern. These perceptions could lead to different priorities in resource allocation and planning for professional development programs. By triangulating findings from surveys, and interviews can provide a comprehensive analysis of the differences in perception between teachers and school heads on challenges related to the implementation of the professional development program. Understanding these differences is crucial in devising strategies that address the concerns of both groups and lead to more effective and supportive professional development initiatives.

5. Level of satisfaction of the teachers and school heads on the implementation of the teacher’s professional development program in terms of the different components

Table 11
Level of Satisfaction of Teachers and School Heads on the Existing Teachers Professional Development Program

Components of Teachers’ Professional Development (TPD)	School Heads		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. School policy for the professional development.	3.71	Very Satisfied	3.68	Very Satisfied
2. Financial resources for Teachers’ Professional Development	2.89	Satisfied	3.80	Very Satisfied
3. Human resources conducting/facilitating the TPD	3.15	Satisfied	3.47	Very Satisfied
4. Material Resources needed for TPD	2.91	Moderately Satisfied	3.61	Very Satisfied

5. Planning aspect for TPD	3.75	Very Satisfied	3.56	Very Satisfied
6. Content and Context of TPD	3.75	Very Satisfied	3.76	Very Satisfied
7. Relevance of the TPD on teachers and learners' needs	3.46	Very Satisfied	3.48	Very Satisfied
8. Teacher Participation/engagement during seminars and training	2.95	Satisfied	3.63	Very Satisfied
9. Support of School Management	3.77	Very Satisfied	3.65	Very Satisfied
10. Duration of seminars and trainings	3	Satisfied	3.60	Very Satisfied
11. Collaboration between and among facilitators/trainer and participants	3.77	Very Satisfied	3.72	Very Satisfied
12. Activities given during seminars and trainings	2.97	Satisfied	3.70	Very Satisfied
13. Attainment of Objectives of the TPDP	3.31	Very Satisfied	3.72	Very Satisfied
14. Selection of teachers who will attend the seminars and trainings and other TPD programs	3.75	Very Satisfied	3.80	Very Satisfied
15. Application of Learnings from the TPD program	2.95	Satisfied	3.33	Very Satisfied
16. Average Weighted Mean	3.38	Very Satisfied	3.64	Very Satisfied

Table 11 reveals the result of the level of satisfaction on the implementation of the teachers' professional development program in terms of the different components of Teachers Professional Development (TPD) the results of the respondents' implementation of the teacher's professional development program in terms of the different components is found to be *very satisfactory*.

The financial resources for teachers' results very satisfied while satisfied for the school head. The two respondents have rated differently for that can arise from a variety of factors related to their roles, perspectives, and experiences within the educational

system. Now that MOOE is present to every school and all the supplies were supported by it on the part of procuring instructional materials for the learners.

On the other hand, material resources have different results on the part of teachers. At present, MOOE funds to every school were used to support the needs of learners in procuring instructional materials to be used and teachers for teachers' professional development. The material resources allocated for TPDP align well with the school's overall goals and strategic plans, the school head might feel satisfied. These resources could include training materials, technology tools, curriculum resources, and other tangible assets that contribute to teacher development and student success.

Meanwhile, teachers rated *very satisfied* on the *teachers' participation* while school heads rated this item *satisfied* because it can be attributed to a variety of factors that influence their perspectives and experiences for some potential reasons for the disparity such as, teachers and school heads have distinct roles during seminars. Teachers are primarily participants seeking to acquire new knowledge and skills, while school heads might view seminars from an organizational and administrative standpoint. Differences in their roles can lead to varying perceptions of participation and engagement. Teachers often have demanding schedules and responsibilities outside of seminars. They might struggle to fully engage if the timing of the seminar conflicts with their teaching duties or personal commitments. School heads, while aware of these constraints, might be evaluating participation from a broader perspective.

Teachers have varied professional development needs and interests. They might perceive the relevance of activities given during seminars and trainings differently based on their subject areas, grade levels and personal teaching goals. On the part of school heads, while considering individual needs might prioritize activities that align more with school's strategic direction.

Teachers' application of learnings from the TPD program had the result of *very satisfied* prior experiences with professional development and its impact on their teaching that can influence their attitudes toward applying new learnings. Positive experiences might lead to more enthusiastic implementation while negative experiences can result in skepticism. For the school heads, might evaluate the application of learnings in terms of its impact on student outcomes and school performance.

Addressing these differences involves effective communication, providing the necessary support and resources, and ensuring that both teachers and school heads understand the broader context in which learnings are applied. Collaborative planning and ongoing dialogue can help bridge the gap between perspectives and promote more effective implementation of learnings from TPDP.

From the findings presented by the study of Northerm (2023), the teachers' levels of exposure to the world rely on many factors such as location, access to information, and socioeconomic status. Moreover, the results indicate that educators can create a level

playing field for all so as with the status, challenges and prospects on teachers' professional development program.

6. Significant difference in the level of satisfaction of teachers on the existing status of teachers' professional development program

Table 12

Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers and School Heads on the Level of Satisfaction of the Existing Status of the Teachers Professional Development Program

Variables	Mean		Probability	Remarks
	School Heads	Teachers		
Perception of the Teachers and School Heads on the Level Status of the Teachers Professional Development Program	3.38	3.64	5.2987E-8	Highly Significant

The Table 12 present the results of the test of significant of the teachers on the existing Teachers Professional Development Program (TPDP) as perceived by the teachers and school heads.

The results reveal that the probability t- value is less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the level of satisfaction of the teachers on the existing TPDP as perceived by the school heads and teachers. It implies that the school heads and the teachers perceived differently the level of satisfaction of the teachers on the existing TPDP. It is stated further as indicated by the mean in the table that the teachers have higher perception on their level of satisfaction on the said existing program than the school heads for, they obtained the higher mean.

The findings regarding the perception of teachers and school heads on the level status of the teachers' professional development program can be highly significant due to several reasons. Addressing the challenges highlighted in the findings can contribute to the sustainability of the professional development program. When educators' needs are met, they are more likely to engage in continuous learning and growth. Result of the conducted interviews with teachers and school heads regarding their perception of the current professional development program; findings revealed that while school heads considered the program to be adequately funded, teachers expressed concerns about the lack of follow-up support and mentoring after training sessions. This discrepancy in perception highlighted the need for additional support structures to be built into the program to enhance its long-term impact on teachers' professional growth.

Integrating findings from interviews, surveys, and existing research, researchers can provide a comprehensive and deep analysis of the perception of teachers and school heads on the status of the professional development program. This analysis can lead to evidence-based recommendations and strategies that enhance the program's impact and support the professional growth of educators.

7. Recommended teachers' prospects to enhance the existing Teachers' Professional Development Program identified by the teachers and school heads

Table 14
Prospects for Teacher's Professional Development Program

Enhancement of the existing teachers' professional development program	Frequency	Rank
1. Must be credited as Continuing Professional Development Units for renewal of professional license.	837	1
2. The existing TPDP must provide for the possibility of achieving further	836	2
3. The TPDP must provide for learning new abilities, earning certifications, gaining more experience in specific field, moving forward in my organization, and pursuing any other career aspirations.	815	3
4. Concepts of the conditions for obtaining further stages of teacher promotion.	813	4
5. The TPDP must improve the skill sets of individuals, and enhances the overall value of being an educator.	812	5
6. It should be a continuing education training with careful planning implementation or application.	811	6
7. It should aim at improving professional competence (various forms of continued education partly or wholly funded by the employer)	807	7
8. Possibility of publishing one's professional observations in methodology and pedagogy.	804	8

9. The TPDP must lead to the improvement of student outcomes and encourage a growth mindset.	803	9
10. Acquiring knowledge, skills and professional competencies during guest visits in the country and abroad.	799	10
11. The TPDP must allow instructors to keep up-to-date on curriculum standards and the latest teaching trends and strategies.	738	11
12. Proper assessment of the school, teachers and learners' needs must be considered as important inputs to a TPD program	678	12

As shown in Table 14, the Continuing Professional Development Units for renewal of professional license must be credited stood as the number one (1) followed by the existing TPDP must provide for the possibility of achieving (2) the TPDP must provide for learning new abilities, earning certifications, gaining more experience in specific field, and moving forward in my organization, and pursuing any other career aspirations in contributing factor of the prospects on Teacher's Professional Development program. Among the 878 teacher-respondents, there were only 837 who answered the highest in rank and 678 for the lowest in rank.

These results have important implications for designing plans and programs of teacher professional development at the schools of Legislative District 2 educational levels.

The study of Postholm (2020), affirms that focusing on teachers' professional development as guided by the influence of school improvement and simply study learning processes. Hence, it is therefore necessary to enhance the existing teachers' professional development program.

Table 15
Prospects for Teacher's Professional Development Program

More development opportunities should be explored to include:	Frequency	Rank
1. Enrollment in formal degree programs, courses, or workshops.	810	1

2. Serving as an officer, board member, or committee member	808	2
3. Learning about new developments in my field	805	3
4. Attending local, regional, national, and international meetings, conferences and workshops sponsored by professional organizations.	801	4
5. Conducting research	798	5
6. Pursue certificates, accreditations or other credentials through educational programs	794	7
7. Improving existing skills taking on new challenges in current position, projects, and long-term assignments.	782	8
8. Keeping up with technology, systems, and processes.	709	9
9. Presenting findings of research to others	635	10
10. Coordinating events sponsored by the organization.	625	11

Table 15 illustrates the prospects on teacher's professional development program in more development opportunities should be explored to include.

It shows that the highest means was given by the teachers only to the enrollment in formal degree programs (810) and the lowest means was given Coordinating events sponsored by the organization (625).

From the study of Kelleher, it affirms that it is no longer sufficient to ask teachers what they thought of a particular workshop session or guest speaker, the issue is not the educator's happiness quotient and how satisfied teachers are with a particular workshop. The prospects on teacher's professional development program in more development opportunities should be explored and has a vital role in identifying different prospects and opportunities on teachers' professional development program.

Conclusions

The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) was fully implemented in Gamu District.

All the areas in the implementation of the BE-LCP were considered as opportunities as perceived by the elementary and secondary school teachers in the district. Although this is true, the same areas were also seen as challenging and very challenging by the elementary and secondary school teachers in the implementation of the BE-LCP. Except governance and operations, which was determined as very challenging, the rest were assessed as challenging by the elementary school teachers. On the part of the secondary school teachers, some areas were gauged as challenging such as curriculum and learning support, modular distance learning, capacity building, requiring health standards to increase physical and mental resilience, and requiring health standards to reduce transmission. While requiring health standards to reduce contact, requiring health standards to reduce duration of infection, stakeholders' engagement and partnership, governance and operations, advocacy and awareness, and monitoring and evaluation were weighed as very challenging.

Based on the findings, the BE-LCP implementation played a significant role in fulfilling the mandate of the Department of Education which is to continue providing quality education to Filipinos despite a crisis as shown in the rise in the number of learners who enrolled, in the increase of participation rate, as well as the decrease in the number of learners who dropped out, both in the elementary and secondary schools. Although completion rate and exit assessments went down in the elementary schools, a complete different picture is shown in the part of the secondary schools since the said indicators rose. These changes in the numbers, however, have marginal effect to the performance of the elementary and secondary schools in the District of Gamu. Only in the decrease of dropout rate had a high and average impact to the performance of the elementary and secondary schools respectively.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. The extent of the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the District of Gamu promotes positive outcomes. Thus, the BE-LCP should be intensified, sustained and maintained by the schools with the support of the teachers, staff and other stakeholders, and work on the area that post challenges.
2. In view of the upskilling and reskilling of teachers, school leaders should focus on professional development for teachers and provide technical assistance to them, so that they will continue to gain knowledge and competencies in order for them to perform their function effectively and efficiently both in the distance and in-person learning process.
3. Schools should continue to practice the DepEd required health standards to ensure the protection of the health, safety and well-being of learners, teachers and personnel, and prevent further transmission of covid-19, and when such similar case may arise in the future.

4. Teachers and school leaders should maintain a good rapport with parents and other stakeholders through giving of feedbacks and suggestions to further improve the schools performance in times such as the covid-19 pandemic as this may help both sides to provide an immediate intervention if issues and problems arise.
5. School leaders and teachers may devise a scheme for monitoring quality assurance to satisfy standard needs and requirements to ensure continued success and quality on implementing the BE-LCP.
6. Similar study maybe is conducted with the inclusion of learners and parents to assess the implementation of the BE-LCP, a bigger sample size, and more school samples.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of Isabela for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

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